

**NEW HIGH SCHOOL: CONTRADICTIONS, CONTINUITIES AND RUPTURES IN
BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL POLICIES**

NUEVA ENSEÑANZA MEDIA: CONTRADICCIONES, PERMANENCIAS Y RUPTURAS EN LAS
POLÍTICAS EDUCATIVAS BRASILEÑAS

NOVO ENSINO MÉDIO: CONTRADIÇÕES, PERMANÊNCIAS E RUPTURAS NAS POLÍTICAS
EDUCACIONAIS BRASILEIRAS

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Abstract

This theoretical essay critically discusses the historical trajectory of Brazilian High School, with emphasis on Law No. 13.415/2017. The analysis, of a historical and critical nature, revisits legal and educational milestones to examine the contradictions, continuities and ruptures that have shaped the policies governing this stage of Basic Education. The discussion underscores the effects on curriculum organization, structural duality, and teaching work, marked by the intensification, precarization, and illness of this professional category. The discussions indicate that, although presented under the discourse of modernization and youth protagonism, the New High School Reform reveals a market-oriented logic that weakens pedagogical autonomy and compromises integral education. The adjustments later implemented by Law No. 14.945/2024 do not eliminate such contradictions but rather reiterate the ongoing cycle of advances and setbacks that has historically characterized High School policies in Brazil.

Keywords: High School; Educational reform; Teaching work; Public policies; Precarization.

Resumen

Este ensayo teórico busca discutir críticamente la trayectoria de la Enseñanza Media brasileña, con énfasis en la Ley nº 13.415/2017. El análisis, de carácter histórico y crítico, visita marcos legales y educativos para verificar las contradicciones, permanencias y rupturas que atraviesan las políticas de

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esta etapa de la Educación Básica. Se destacan los efectos sobre la organización curricular, la dualidad estructural y el trabajo docente, marcado por la intensificación, precarización y enfermedad de esta categoría. Las discusiones indican que, aunque presentada bajo el discurso de modernización y protagonismo juvenil, la reforma de la Nueva Enseñanza Media (Novo Ensino Médio) revela una lógica de mercado que fragiliza la autonomía pedagógica y compromete la formación integral. Los ajustes realizados posteriormente por la Ley nº 14.945/2024 no eliminan tales contradicciones, sino que reiteran el movimiento de avances y retrocesos que caracteriza históricamente las políticas de la Enseñanza Media brasileña.

Palabras Clave: Enseñanza Media; Reforma educativa; Trabajo docente; Políticas públicas; Precarización.

Resumo

Este ensaio teórico busca discutir criticamente a trajetória do Ensino Médio brasileiro, com ênfase na Lei nº 13.415/2017. A análise, de caráter histórico e crítico, visita marcos legais e educacionais para verificação de contradições, permanências e rupturas que atravessam as políticas dessa etapa do Ensino Básico. Destacam-se os efeitos sobre a organização curricular, a dualidade estrutural e o trabalho docente, marcado pela intensificação, precarização e adoecimento dessa categoria. As discussões indicam que, embora apresentada sob o discurso de modernização e protagonismo juvenil, a reforma do Novo Ensino Médio revela uma lógica mercadológica que fragiliza a autonomia pedagógica e compromete a formação integral. Os ajustes realizados posteriormente, pela Lei nº 14.945/2024, não eliminam tais contradições, mas reiteram o movimento de avanços e retrocessos que caracteriza historicamente as políticas do Ensino Médio brasileiro.

Palavras-chave: Ensino Médio; Reforma educacional; Trabalho docente; Políticas públicas; Precarização.

Introduction

Brazil's most recent High School reform, introduced by Law No. 13.415/2017 (Brasil, 2017) and later partially amended by Law No. 14.945/2024 (Brasil, 2024b), brought significant changes to the policies governing this stage of Basic Education. Known as the New High School, these reforms were justified by the need to promote a more flexible curriculum, foster youth protagonism, and make schools more relevant to the world of work (Habowski; Leite, 2022).

However, the implementation of this proposal has revealed significant impacts, particularly with regard to teachers' working conditions. As highlighted by Soares (2024, p. 107), the implementation of this policy "brought with it a series of challenges that affect not only classroom dynamics, but also teachers' working conditions, the quality of basic education, and the health of these professionals."

The precariousness of teaching work, especially in High School, has intensified and has become one of the main challenges in the Brazilian educational landscape. This process, understood as the progressive weakening of working conditions and professional recognition, results from a combination of neoliberal educational policies, structural reforms with limited institutional support, and the intensification of demands placed on the teaching professional (Pereira, 2022).

These changes have generated extensive debates among researchers, educators, and administrators, particularly regarding their implications for teaching practice (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization – UNESCO, 2024). The Brazilian educational context, historically marked by inequalities and structural challenges, imposes severe limitations on working conditions, the appreciation of the teaching career, and the promotion of more qualified pedagogical practices.

Within this scenario, the implementation of educational reforms has prompted discussions that address not only policy and curricular adjustments but also broader effects on teachers' daily lives. There has been a noticeable intensification of an ongoing process of precariousness in teaching work, manifested through work overload, low salaries, contractual instability, and a lack of institutional support (Previtali; Fagiani, 2020). These factors contribute to an increase in cases of physical and mental illness among teachers, compromising not only professional performance but also the retention of professionals in the career (Soares, 2024).

Given this context, this essay seeks to critically discuss the historical trajectory of Brazilian High School, with an emphasis on Law No. 13.415/2017, highlighting its implications for curriculum organization, structural duality, and teaching work.

Theoretical-reflective journey

This study adopts a qualitative approach (Mussi *et al.*, 2019) and is characterized as a theoretical essay with a critical-reflective orientation. One of the defining features of this academic genre is its originality, expressed through its propositional capacity to offer a singular and critical reading of the object under analysis (Soares; Picolli; Casagrande, 2018).

The essay is grounded in a narrative literature review (Rother, 2007) which serves as the methodological strategy for selecting and analyzing sources. This process draws on legal

frameworks, academic studies, and official documents in order to critically examine the continuities, ruptures, and contradictions present in educational policies related to High School. A Literature review is useful for highlighting how topics have been addressed within different fields of knowledge (Almeida *et al.*, 2024). By adopting this approach, the analysis becomes contextualized and interpretative, emphasizing the authors' viewpoints and offering an up-to-date theoretical overview of the subject.

Contextualizing High School

High School in Brazil had its institutional origin in 1837, with the creation of the Dom Pedro II College in Rio de Janeiro, the first High School institution⁴ in the country (Santos, 2010). The founding of this school was associated with the need for intellectual training of national leaders, revealing from its inception the elitist character that would mark Brazilian education. From that point onward, education underwent several reforms, always influenced by political, economic, and social contexts, which significantly impacted its curricular, organizational, and pedagogical structures (Mendonça; Fialho, 2020).

During the Imperial period (1821-1889), High School primarily functioned as preparation for students' entry into Higher Education (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022). This elite-oriented perspective persisted during the Old Republic (1889-1930), despite important reforms, such as the Benjamin Constant Reform of 1890, which established a seven-year duration for High School, and the João Luís Alves Reform of 1925, which reduced this period to five years (Santos, 2010). Access therefore remained restricted to privileged social groups, highlighting the persistence of an exclusionary educational model (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022).

With Getúlio Vargas' rise to power in 1930, the State increased investment in technical and vocational education, considered strategic for meeting labor market demands. This movement culminated in the Gustavo Capanema Reform of 1942, which structured High School into two courses: the scientific and the classical⁵, both aimed at preparing students

⁴ According to Silva (1969), the term 'High School' designates a level of the educational process corresponding to high school, secondary education or post-primary education.

⁵ In the classical course, intellectual development will include, in addition to a greater knowledge of philosophy, a pronounced study of ancient literature; in the scientific course, this development will be marked

for entry into Higher Education (Santos, 2010). As Ribeiro (1993) noted, this formal differentiation did not materialize in practice, since both courses maintained a humanistic, encyclopedic, and elitist foundation, distancing High School from the needs of the popular classes and reinforcing educational duality.

The 1940s were marked by significant transformations in Brazil, driven by the end of World War II, political changes, and growing pressure to democratize access to education (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022).

In this context, the 1946 Constitution, in Article 168, indicated the need for comprehensive educational legislation (Brasil, 1946). With the end of the Estado Novo (New State), the path was opened for the elaboration of the first Law of Guidelines and Bases (LDB), Law No. 4.024/1961 (Ramos, 2014). This legislation aimed to ensure adolescents' schooling and to establish equivalence between High School and technical and pedagogical courses (Brasil, 1961). Even so, the law failed to overcome inequalities in access, reaffirming selectivity and social exclusion (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022).

Following the 1964 military coup, education came to be understood as an instrument for economic development and as a mechanism of ideological control, in line with agreements between the Ministry of Education and international organizations (Habowski; Leite, 2022). Law No. 5.692/1971, which reformed the LDB of 1961, reinforced this logic by redefining curricular guidelines for High School and by emphasizing the training of a qualified workforce for the labor market (Brasil, 1971). As a result, the preparatory character of High School was reduced, while technical and vocational training gained greater prominence (Ramos, 2014).

The history of High School in Brazil is therefore marked by constant disputes and contradictions. During the country's redemocratization process in the late 1980s and early 1990s, education once again assumed a central position in public policy debates (Pereira, 2022). In the discussions of the Constituent Assembly that resulted in the 1988 Federal Constitution, different political groups contested distinct educational projects (Habowski; Leite, 2022). Despite the disputes, the new Constitution reaffirmed education as a social

by a greater study of sciences. Available at: <https://www.histedbr.fe.unicamp.br/navegando/acervos/decreto-lei-4244-1942-reforma-capanema-ensino-secundario>. Accessed on: April 4, 2025.

right, redefining the foundations of High School and reinforcing the importance of providing qualified education for Brazilian youth (Brasil, 1996).

Public educational policies for High School in contemporary times

In a country characterized by its diversity and inequality, such as Brazil, public education policies occupy a central place in the struggle for social rights and civic education. The historical trajectory of High School reveals a field marked by advances and setbacks, in which each reform exposes clashes arising from political, economic, and ideological interests. Far from building consensus, these policies express tensions about the meaning of school, the role of teachers, and the relationship between education and the market.

- The 1996 Law of Guidelines and Bases (LDB) and its initial amendments

The enactment of Law No. 9.394/1996 represented a milestone in the organization of Basic Education, structuring it into three stages: Early Childhood Education, Elementary Education, and High School. This legal framework signaled the consolidation of an ethical and autonomous education project, seeking to break with the historical dichotomy between Technical Education and Higher Education (Brasil, 1996).

However, under the strong influence of the neoliberal context of the 1990s (Pereira, 2022), this curricular reorganization failed to overcome the historical duality of the Brazilian education system. Tensions persisted between the goal of providing Integral Education for students and the adaptation of school to the immediate demands of the market (Ávila, 2023).

Decree No. 2.208/1997 reinforced this movement by separating technical vocational training from High School, establishing it as an independent education pathway (Brasil, 1997). This measure once again ruled out the possibility of curricular integration and was widely regarded as a setback, as it formalized the exclusion of vocational education from Basic Education and reinstated educational duality. As observed by Saviani (2018, p. 297):

[...] **such a measure** represented a step backward, not only in relation to Law No. 5.692/1971, but also in relation to the LDB (Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education) of 1961. The latter had made the relationship between the branches of

high school more flexible at the time, allowing equivalence and transition between them, thus breaking the "duality of systems" characteristic of the Capanema reforms of the 1940s, during the Estado Novo (New State) period. It is precisely to this duality that the aforementioned decree returned.

In the late 1990s, new policy instruments were introduced. The National High School Examination (ENEM), established in 1998 by Decree No. 438, began to function as a mechanism for assessing students' skills and competencies (Brasil, 1998). The following year, the National Curriculum Parameters for High School (PCNEM) organized the curriculum into three areas of knowledge, emphasizing the development of skills and competencies (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022).

Although presented under a discourse of modernization, these initiatives reflected an evaluative and classificatory logic that aligned school with external demands, subordinating comprehensive education to performance on standardized assessments.

- Expansion and Reform Policies (2001 – 2016)

The beginning of the 21st century marked a phase of expansion and reconfiguration of policies aimed at High School. Law No. 10.172/2001 established the new National Education Plan (PNE), valid for ten years, determining that states and municipalities should develop their own educational plans, while the Union would be responsible for the National Evaluation System and monitoring the established goals (Brasil, 2001). In that same year, the ENEM became recognized as a mechanism for access to Higher Education (Ávila, 2023), signaling the central role that evaluation would assume in educational policies.

Decree N°. 5.154/2004 (Brasil, 2004) established Integrated High School (EMI), aiming to overcome the fragmentation between Basic Education and Professional Education and to affirm work as an educational principle. According to Ramos (2011), this proposal represented a counter-hegemonic initiative amid the predominance of neoliberal policies, as it ensured a focus on knowledge and sought comprehensive human development.

According to Pereira (2022), the EMI aimed for students to develop a critical understanding of reality, fostering the intellectual to question and transform labor relations within the capitalist order. However, its implementation encountered political and structural

limitations, demonstrating how significant advances coexist with the historical contradictions of Brazilian education.

In 2008, the results of the National High School Examination (ENEM) began to be used to grant scholarships for Higher Education in private institutions through the University for All Program (ProUni). From 2009 onwards, ENEM assumed a central role as the primary mechanism for access to Higher Education in universities (Ávila, 2023). In 2010, the Unified Selection System (SISU) further expanded its centrality, making ENEM practically mandatory for High School students (Brasil, 2010). As highlighted by Alves, Silva and Jucá (2022, p. 146),

[...] ENEM (National High School Examination) became mandatory for all high school students and acquired the function of a systemic, certifying, and classificatory assessment. This development significantly impacted the structuring of high school curricula, and many schools began to pursue passing ENEM as the main objective of high school.

This focus on ENEM performance, geared toward university admission, led to an adjustment in education practices, which has directed its focus on the demands of the examination to the detriment of broader and more diverse education aims, thereby compromising pedagogical autonomy and reinforcing educational inequalities.

In parallel, the Innovative High School Program (ProEMI), created in 2009 (Brasil, 2009), sought to overcome educational duality through curricular flexibility and continuing teacher training (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022). Despite its potential, the program depended on technical and financial support conditioned by specific agreements (Ramos, 2011), revealing the unstable nature of public education policies, which often fail to consolidate as state policies and instead remain tied to government projects characterized by discontinuity and institutional fragility (Oliveira, 2011).

Bill No. 6.840-A/2013 (Brasil, 2013), drafted by the Special Committee for the Reformulation of High School (CEENSI) of the Chamber of Deputies, intensified the debate surrounding the proposal of a reform justified by the claim that the existing curriculum was

[...] outdated, extremely overloaded, with excessive content, formal, standardized, with many mandatory subjects in a dynamic that does not recognize the individual and geographical differences of the students. (Brasil, 2013, p. 8)

This proposal reinforced the discourse on the need to make education more attractive to young people and to align it with the demands of the labor market (Brasil,

2013). According to Pereira's analysis (2022), Bill No. 6.840/2013 presented the same guidelines advocated by the movement Todos pela Educação (All for Education), prioritizing curricular flexibility, increased teaching hours, and closer ties between schools and the productive sector—measures that reflect the aspirations of the dominant classes and shift the focus from comprehensive education toward adaptation to economic demands.

In opposition to this perspective, the National Movement in Defense of High School was created in 2014, formed by academic entities, unions, and social movements, in opposition to the logic of the reform centered on employability and curricular flexibility (Pereira, 2022), which was seen as detriment to the integral education of students.

In the same year, the Ministry of Education (MEC) launched the new National Education Plan (PNE), establishing 20 goals to be achieved by 2024 (Brasil, 2014). The idea of a national education plan with defined objectives, originally proposed during the Francisco Campos Reform under Getúlio Vargas's government in 1931, was only realized decades later, following successive revisions and modifications across different governments (Vieira; Ramalho; Vieira, 2017).

In October 2016, the Program to Promote Full-Time Secondary Schools (EMTI) was established by Ordinance No. 1.145, with the proposal focused on extending students' time in school and promoting a more comprehensive education (Brasil, 2016). Although it represented a promising initiative to extend school time, Andrade and Duarte (2023) highlight that its implementation was limited and heterogeneous among the states, since it was conditional on voluntary participation and the transfer of specific resources, which configured its provisional character and, therefore, the fragility of this policy.

- The reform of High School and Law No. 13.415/2017

The year 2017 marked the implementation of the reform of High School in Brazil with the enactment of Law No. 13.415, resulting from Provisional Measure No. 746/2016 (Brasil, 2016). According to the legal text, Article 35-A, §7, item IV establishes that "High School curricula must consider the integral formation of the student in order to adopt practices focused on the construction of their life project and their development in physical, cognitive and socio-emotional dimensions" (Brasil, 2017).

Among the main changes, the following stand out: the increase in the minimum annual workload from 800 to 1,000 hours and the curricular reorganization articulating the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC), responsible for common and mandatory content, with the formative itineraries, which allow students to direct their in-depth study according to their interests and aptitudes. These itineraries were structured into five areas of knowledge: Languages and their Technologies, Natural Sciences and their Technologies, Human and Social Sciences Applied, Mathematics and its Technologies, and Technical and Professional Training (Brasil, 2017).

Furthermore, the formative itineraries, according to Souza (2024, p. 769, author's emphasis), “contain an integrating core formed by **elective subjects, Life Project, in addition to the in-depth study track**”. The Life Project proposal, provided for in Article 35-A, § 7 of the LDB, as amended by Law No. 13.415/2017, aims to guide students to reflect on their personal, professional, and social trajectories, promoting responsible and conscious decision-making (Brasil, 2017).

However, as observed by Souza (2024), this conception of integral education, anchored in the notion of a "life project" tends to individualize responsibility for educational success, shifting the focus from the structural conditions of the school to student's individual performance and choices. Thus, the reform consolidated changes that negatively impacted curricular organization and teaching work in subsequent years.

- Developments and questions after the reform (2018-2023)

Following the enactment of Law No. 13.415/2017 (Brasil, 2017), various regulations and events marked the implementation of the New High School curriculum. In November 2018, Resolution No. 3 was approved, updating the National Curriculum Guidelines for High School (DCENEM) (Brasil, 2018) and reinforcing the perspectives established by Law, No. 13.415/2017.

In 2020 and 2021, the emergency period of the COVID-19 pandemic ⁶and the resulting phase of social isolation directly impacted schools. The lack of adequate preparation and unequal access to digital resources negatively impacted the quality of classes, as remote teaching required real-time interaction and access to digital support materials (Farina; Benvenuti, 2024).

In 2022, Resolution No. 192 approved the regulations for High School within the Bahia State Education System (Brasil, 2022). In 2023, following a change in federal administration, Ordinance No. 627/2023 (Brasil, 2023a) suspended the implementation of the New High School for 60 days, proposing the organization of public debates and a reassessment of the policy. In the same year, Bill No. 5.230/2023 amended Law No. 9.394/1996, redefining the guidelines of the national High School policy (Brasil, 2023b).

- Latest guidelines and Law No. 14.945/2024

In March of 2024, the Chamber of Deputies approved, in a symbolic vote, the base text of Bill No. 5.230/2023 (Brasil, 2023), which introduced changes to the existing structure of the New High School. In July of the same year, Law No. 14.945/2024 (Brasil, 2024b) was instituted, which restructured High School, amended Law No. 9.394/1996 (Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education) and partially repealed Law No. 13.415/2017.

Figure 1 shows the main changes to the High School curriculum effective from 2025 onward. The reform increase the workload of general basic education from 1,800 hours to 2,400 hours, ensuring more instructional time dedicated to common curricular components. Conversely, the workload allocated to elective pathways was reduced from 1,200 hours to 600 hours. This change applies exclusively for Integrated High School, while the workload for regular High School remains unchanged.

⁶ COVID-19 is an acute respiratory infection caused by the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus , potentially serious, highly transmissible and with a global distribution (Brasil, 2021).

Figure 1 – Main changes in the High School curriculum under Law No. 14.945/2024

Source: Prepared by the authors based on Law No. 14.945/2024 (2025) ⁷.

The changes established by Law No. 14.945/2024 came into effect in 2025 and are being implemented gradually, beginning with the first grade of High School in 2025, followed by the second grade in 2026 and, finally the third grade in 2027 (Brasil, 2024b).

Also in 2024, Law No. 14.818/2024, enacted on January 16, established a financial educational incentive program in the form of savings accounts for students enrolled in public High School (Brasil, 2024a). The law amended Laws No. 13.999/2020 and No. 14.075/2020 and created the Pé-de-Meia Program, whose objective is to promote students' permanence in school until the completion of this education stage (Brasil, 2024a).

Table 1 summarizes the evolution of High School in Brazil between 1996 and 2025. It illustrates a structural reconfiguration of High School, in which the expansion of the general education workload and the redefinition of formative pathways generated new challenges for schools and teachers. These changes, while representing an attempt to correct distortions in the previous model, highlight the persistence of tensions between the pursuit of comprehensive education and the productivity demands imposed by market logic.

⁷Available at: <https://www.gov.br/mec/pt-br/assuntos/noticias/2024/agosto/sancionada-lei-que-reestrutura-o-ensino-medio>. Accessed on: 02/14/2025.

Table 1 – Evolution of the High School in Brazil.

Year	Event / Standard	Description
1996	LDBEN - Law No. 9.394	Defines High School as the final stage of Basic Education and allows for integrated or separate technical training.
1997	Decree No. 2.208	Separates technical education from general education, reinforcing the educational duality.
1998	Creation of the ENEM (Decree No. 438/1998)	Establishes a national assessment for graduating High School students.
1999	PCNEM	Defines national curriculum guidelines for High School, emphasizing competencies and skills.
2001	National Education Plan (Law No. 10.172/2001)	Establishes goals and responsibilities for federal entities, states, and municipalities in education.
2004	Decree No. 5.154	Establishes Integrated High School (EMI), linking High School, Elementary and Technical Education with a focus on comprehensive human development.
2008	ENEM becomes a criterion for ProUni	Expands the use of ENEM scores to grant scholarships at private Higher Education institutions.
2009	Creation of ProEMI (Decree No. 971/2009)	Promotes curricular flexibility and innovation in High School.
2010	Creation of SISU (Normative Ordinance No. 2/2010)	Establishes a computerized system using ENEM scores for admission to public High Education institutions.
2013	Bill No. 6.840-A/2013 and the creation of CEENSI	Proposes reform High School, generating criticism and the creation of the National Movement in Defense of High School.
2014	New National Education Plan (Law No. 13.005/2014)	Establishes 20 national goals, including universal access to High School.
2016	EMTI (Ordinance No. 1.145/2016)	Encourages the expansion of full-time high schools program.
2017	High School Reform (Law No. 13.415/2017)	Restructures High School, introducing formative pathways and revising the curriculum structure based on the BNCC (National Common Core Curriculum).
2018	Resolution No. 3/2018 (DCNEM)	Updates the National Curriculum Guidelines for High School in accordance with Law No. 13.415/2017.
2020 2021	COVID-19 Pandemic	Disrupts the education system as a whole, accelerating remote learning and exposing structural inequalities.
2022	Resolution No. 192/2022 (Bahia)	Regulates High School within the Bahia State Education System.
2023	Bill No. 5.230/2023 and Ordinance No. 627/2023	Temporarily suspends the implementation of the New High School curriculum and initiates policy reassessment.
2024	Law No. 14.945/2024	Restructures High School and partially repeals Law No. 13.415/2017.

Source: Prepared by the authors (2025).

- Precariousness of teaching work – concepts and general overview

The precariousness of work has become one of the defining features of contemporary capitalism. Since the 1970s, economic crises, transformations in the organization of production, and new mechanisms of capital accumulation have led to the erosion of rights historically secured by the working class (Santos, 2023). This process is

associated with the flexibilization of labor relations, the expansion of informal employment, and the reduction of social protections.

According to Piovezan (2017), this scenario reflects a progressive dismantling of the protections ensured by the Welfare State, particularly in developed countries, where social policies in the areas of health, education, social security, and transportation had been structured throughout the 20th century. The author further argues that productive restructuring and globalization intensified this process, imposing a labor logic marked by instability, outsourcing, and the expansion of precarious contracts.

The term "precarious work" has been used in the literature to characterize the new labor configurations that emerged after the 1970s (Piovezan, 2017). From this perspective, Rosenfield (2011, p. 264) defines precarious work as "socially impoverished, unskilled, informal, temporary and insecure work," emphasizing that precarization constitutes a social process through which instability becomes institutionalized.

Druck (2012) expands this analysis by arguing that the precarization of work manifests itself in various dimensions, including hiring methods, informality, outsourcing, deregulation and flexibilization of labor legislation, as well as unemployment, wage reduction, and the weakening of unions. Viegas and Lamb (2025) further highlight that precarization has intensified through the platformization and digitalization of work, generating mechanisms of exploitation and control.

In Brazilian education, one of the most striking features of contemporary capitalism has been the precarization of labor, intensified by the educational reforms of the 1990s, aligned with neoliberal policies and productivism restructuring (Santos, 2023). These changes promoted the flexibilization of labor relations and consolidated the commodification of education, negatively affecting the teaching profession.

The precariousness of teaching work manifests itself both in the limited financial and administrative investments by the State and in inadequate working conditions, combined with an overload of tasks (Oliveira, 2004). Teachers face large classes, diverse social contexts, and an exclusionary school dynamic, marked by efforts to ensure student permanence in school without guarantees of the structural conditions necessary for quality education (Andrade; Falcão, 2018).

Some of the most common factors contributing to the precariousness of teaching work include low salaries, accumulation of functions, a lack of adequate teaching resources, and inadequate infrastructure. According to Oliveira and Pires (2014, p. 94),

[...] discussing the precariousness of teaching work without mentioning some aspects of the *work environment* is not appropriate, as the relationship between teachers and the environmental conditions in which work constitutes one of the main factors contributing to teacher burnout, and its implications directly affect the health of Brazilian teachers.

In this sense, both the structural conditions of the work environment and changes in production dynamics contribute to the weakening of the teaching profession and to deterioration of the quality of teaching work.

In the Brazilian context, the precariousness of teaching work has been aggravated by constant educational reforms that impose new demands without guaranteeing adequate working conditions (Santos, 2023). Among the most recent is the reform of High School, instituted by Law No. 13.415/2017 (Brasil, 2017), which, even before being consolidated, was partially repealed and subsequently restructured by Law No. 14.945/2024 (Brasil, 2024b).

These laws increased the minimum total workload to 3,000 hours across the three years of High School (Brasil, 2024c), requiring teachers to dedicate more instructional time without corresponding salary adjustments, continuing professional development, or improvements in school infrastructure. According to Souza (2024), this scenario contributes to the blaming of teachers, who are often held responsible for poor academic performance while the difficult conditions under which educational work is carried out are disregarded.

This precariousness is expressed, for example, in increasingly larger classes and the requirement to plan lessons across multiple curricular components, sometimes outside teachers' areas of training (Dildey, 2023).

In this scenario, work intensification and curricular fragmentation impose additional challenges on High School teachers, who need to adapt to new pedagogical demands without adequate support. The increase in bureaucratic tasks, lack of recognition, devaluation of the profession, and insufficient school infrastructure compromise not only the quality of education but also the physical and mental health of teachers (Forattini; Lucena, 2015; Honda; Cardoso; Mussi, 2025).

Given this, careful discussion is needed on how this precarious situation affects not only educational outcomes, but also the identity formation and health of teachers.

Analytical dimensions and reflections on the New High School

The theoretical reflection constructed from official documents, academic productions, and institutional reports on the New High School curriculum allows for the identification of a set of structural contradictions that characterize this educational policy. These contradictions manifest themselves in five interdependent dimensions: "Minimum training," "Curriculum fragmentation and inequality of access," "Precariousness of teaching work," "Teacher illness and quality of life," and "State response."

- Minimum training

The New High School reveals a contradiction in which the expansion of the school day from four to seven hours did not result in a comprehensive education. As Albuquerque *et al.* (2020) point out, the increased time spent at school reinforced the fragmentation of education, marked by the absence of content in social, philosophical, and artistic fields, as well as by limited connection with the students' reality.

Ramos and Frigotto (2017, p. 42) criticize this logic by stating that: "[...] the children of the working class [...] will have access to a minimum of High School, with a minimum level of training for an equally minimum life [...]", demonstrating the existence of a policy that transfers responsibility for human development to the market.

From a historical perspective, this trend is not new. Santos (2010) pointed out that, before the Capanema Reform in 1942, High School was already structured in a dual manner, reserving classical and scientific courses for the elite, while technical pathways were directed towards the productive demands of the working class. Saviani (2018) adds that this duality has not disappeared over the decades, but has been continuously updated through reforms, as occurred with Decree No. 2.208/1997 (Brasil, 1997), which separated Technical Education from General Education, restricting the popular classes' access to comprehensive and integrated knowledge.

In light of this context, the High School reform implemented in 2017 represented an update to this long-standing historical process, in which the expansion of school time did not necessarily imply comprehensiveness, but rather the maintenance of an exclusionary and restrictive model that continues to reproduce educational inequalities in Brazil.

- Curricular fragmentation and unequal access

Another aspect associated with the contradictions of the New High School is curricular fragmentation. The implementation of the reform resulted in the creation of hundreds of elective curricular components distributed across the formative pathways, diversifying and fragmenting the curriculum across different regions of the country. This flexibility generated a wide range of curricular components, ultimately producing significant differences among schools, states, and regions, thereby compromising the continuity and equivalence of studies for students who needed to transfer between education systems.

A survey conducted by the newspaper *Folha de S. Paulo* (2023), based on information from state education departments, identified the creation of at least 1,526 new curricular components as part of the implementation of the New High School curriculum. Figure 2 presents the number of curricular components offered per state, according to the newspaper's survey.

In addition to the wide variety of subjects offered throughout the country, the data reveal a lack of standardization. In Piauí, for example, students had access to seven different subjects, while in the Federal District the number rose to 601 options (*Folha de São Paulo*, 2023). These differences highlight the structural inequalities of the Brazilian educational system and reinforce the exclusionary logic of the New High School curriculum, which, in addition to not guaranteeing a comprehensive and equitable education, deepens the differences in access to educational opportunities.

From a historical perspective, this fragmentation also finds its roots in the reforms of the 1990s, when the National Curriculum Parameters for High School in 1999 emphasized competencies and skills, without concern for resolving the structural heterogeneity of the system (Alves; Silva; Jucá, 2022). Furthermore, the emergency phase of the COVID-19

pandemic (2020-2021) exacerbated inequalities, as not all networks had sufficient digital resources and support to maintain classes, widening the inequality among students (Farina; Benvenuti, 2024).

Figure 2 – Number of curricular components offered in the New High School by Brazilian state.

*In additional to other components created by each school.

Source: State Education Departments

Source: Folha de S. Paulo (2023).

In the daily teaching practice, this curricular fragmentation has frequently required teachers to teach components outside their areas of training, in unequal contexts and without institutional support (Souza, 2024). Thus, a policy conceived to expand education opportunities, yet disconnected from school reality, ultimately reinforcing exclusions, both in students' access and in the conditions of pedagogical work.

- Precarious working conditions for teachers

The landscape of teaching work within the New High School context has revealed an intensification of professional precariousness. Factors such as overload, low salaries, temporary contracts, and lack of institutional support have accentuated the devaluation on the profession, as well as illness and burnout among teachers (Soares, 2024; Honda; Cardoso; Mussi, 2025).

According to Ávila's analysis (2023), a significant number of teachers reported the absence of adequate spaces for developing classes in the formative itineraries, highlighting the scarcity of classrooms and necessary pedagogical resources, such as laboratories. As a result, teachers began to teach the new curricular components using the same available resources, without the necessary infrastructure improvement or adaptations required for the effective implementation of the New High School curriculum.

Even in schools with infrastructure considered satisfactory, challenges persist. As Souza (2024) observed, school units that had air-conditioned classrooms, an enclosed sports court, changing rooms, and adequate availability of resources also faced difficulties in implementing the changes required by the reform.

Among the main challenges identified were the absence of qualified teachers to teach the new curricular components and the work overload resulting from the fragmentation of teaching schedules. In addition, there was the lack of sufficient curricular and pedagogical guidelines for the effective development of elective curricular components, as well as disorganization of classes and a widespread sense of professional delegitimization among teachers (Souza, 2024). This account demonstrates that the challenges are not limited to the deficiencies of physical infrastructure, but also to the incompatibility between existing conditions and the demands imposed by educational policy.

Recent studies confirm the worsening of this scenario. A survey conducted by Todos Pela Educação (2024) indicated that, since 2023, temporary teachers have already exceeded the number of permanent teachers in state schools, reaching 51.6% of the total workforce. Similarly, research conducted by the Instituto Inteligência em Pesquisa e Consultoria Estratégica (IPEC) showed that at least 71% of Brazilian teachers reported experiencing symptoms of stress due to work overload (Agência Brasil, 2023).

In this context, a study conducted by UNESCO (2024), in collaboration with the Ministry of Education (MEC), carried out the New High School Survey, collecting data on the perceptions of the students, teachers, and school administrators regarding the first year of implementation of the New High School, which began in 2022, for first-grade classes. Teachers constituted the group that expressed the highest level of dissatisfaction, with 76% reporting negative evaluations of the reform.

The same study also found that, among the country's regions, the highest levels of dissatisfaction were recorded in the Central-West (85%), whereas the South, with 69%, presented the lowest rate. The data indicate that dissatisfaction exceeded satisfaction in all regions, reinforcing the contradictions between the discourse of modernization associated with the New High School and the concrete effects of its implementation.

Beyond the objective conditions of precariousness, there have also been direct impacts on teacher training and identity. Dilley (2023) highlighted that the reform of High School required teachers to teach curricular components outside their area of training, revealing the structural inadequacy of the policy in relation to concrete working conditions. In the same vein, Souza (2024, p. 769) emphasized that "teachers are asked to teach classes that are not specific to their training, leading to a loss of professional identity within their teaching areas."

These recent data confirm trends identified in the critical literature on teaching work. For Santos (2023), precarization intensified from the 1990s onwards, when educational reforms aligned with neoliberal ideology promoted the flexibilization of labor relations and the commodification of education. Piovezan (2017) adds that, during this same period, there was a progressive dismantling of the protections ensured by the Welfare State, imposing more unstable and unprotected conditions on the working class in general, and on teachers in particular.

Druck (2012) highlighted that precarization is expressed across multiple dimensions, including the expansion of outsourcing, the growth of informality, the deregulation of labor rights, and the weakening of unions, configuring a scenario marked by the erosion of professional protection and recognition. Thus, it is reasonable to understand that the reform of High School did not initiate the process of precarization within the educational system, but it has certainly intensified it, since it reaffirms the historical trajectory of devaluation and vulnerability of the teaching profession.

- Teacher illness and quality of life

Teacher illness is one of the most visible expressions of the inadequate working conditions imposed by recent educational reforms. According to Castro Neta, Cardoso and Nunes (2020), physical and mental health problems among teachers result from the intensification of institutional demands, low salaries, and a lack of professional support and recognition.

According to Barros, Seixas, and Cardoso (2022), the demands placed on teachers lead to symptoms such as stress, anxiety, and depression, affecting physical, psychological, and personal dimensions of health, with direct repercussions on their quality of life. Oliveira and Pires (2014) add that aspects of the work environment, such as overcrowded classrooms, inadequate infrastructure, and lack of pedagogical resources, contribute to teachers' physical and emotional exhaustion, thereby compromising their quality of life. For the authors, "the health of the worker is closely related to their work environment" (Oliveira; Pires, 2014, p. 94).

Similarly, Forattini and Lucena (2015) argue that inadequate working conditions associated with increased bureaucratic demands and pressure for results, lead to professional burnout and occupational stress. Soares (2024) reinforces that, when dealing with large classes and diverse social contexts, teachers face not only pedagogical challenges, but also an exclusionary and exhausting dynamic that directly affect their quality of life, as well as their retention and motivation.

Beyond the physical dimensions, illness involves the loss of meaning and professional identity. Souza (2024) highlighted the process of teacher blaming, in which responsibility for school failure is transferred to teachers, disregarding the material conditions under which the work is carried out. According to the author, this logic ignores both the structural inadequacies of schools and the overload of responsibilities and curricular fragmentation, generating feelings of powerlessness and intensifying psychological suffering.

The disconnection from teacher's areas of training, together with the requirement to teach curricular components outside their area of expertise (Dilley, 2023), coupled with the loss of social recognition of the profession, contribute to a process of deprofessionalization (Oliveira, 2004).

This scenario weakens the essential connection between teachers and their pedagogical practices, negatively affecting self-esteem and motivation and, consequently, their quality of life, while also compromising the quality of education provided.

- State response

Regarding the State's capacity to respond, criticism and pressure from civil society, student movements, and teachers pressure the federal government to revise its policy concerning the New High School curriculum. In this context, the public consultation held in 2023 stands out, as it collected input from students, teachers, and administrators regarding the future of High School in Brazil (Brasil, 2023c). This process resulted in the enactment of Law No. 14.945/2024, which partially repealed Law No. 13.415/2017 and established gradual changes beginning in 2025 (Brasil, 2024b).

However, the implementation of the changes is uneven between states and municipalities, highlighting both structural disparities and political and institutional resistance. The oscillation between advances and setbacks is not new in the history of Brazilian education. The 1961 LDB sought equivalence between educational pathways (Ramos, 2014), the 1996 LDB reorganized Basic Education. In contrast, the 2017 educational counter-reform reinstated the dual logic, denying the popular classes full access to knowledge, and reinforcing the dichotomy between academic and vocational education, as well as between public and private education (Pereira, 2022).

According to Habowski and Leite (2022), educational reforms have historically reflected disputes among different power groups and their interests, resulting in partial responses that are generally insufficient to address the structural inequalities in Brazilian education.

Thus, although the State's response sometimes demonstrates sensitivity to social criticism, a logic of compensatory and partial reforms persists, incapable of promoting the necessary rupture with the structural duality that weakens High School.

Final considerations

From the enactment of the Law of Guidelines and Bases of National Education (LDBEN/1996), to the implementation of Law No. 14.945/2024, educational reforms in Brazil have been and continue to be conducted predominantly to meet demands imposed by the capitalist economic model, often disregarding the context of social inequality that characterizes the country.

The new policy for High School in Brazil, with its proposal for curricular flexibility and formative pathways, faces challenges both to the quality of education and to teachers' working conditions. The fragmentation of the curriculum into multiple curricular components, frequently taught by teachers without specific training in the respective area, combined with the reduction of instructional time for general education components and the expansion of teaching assignments, not only compromises the teaching-learning process but also intensifies and further precarizes teachers' work.

The impacts of these changes manifest across different dimensions, including work overload due to multiple planning demands, the need to adapt to new curricular components, the intensification of bureaucratic requirements, and pressure for results without adequate structural support. These conditions increase the risk of physical and mental illness among teachers, contribute to the deprofessionalization of teaching, and compromise the quality of education.

Although Law No. 13.415/2017 was partially repealed by Law No. 14.945/2024, the structural problems that undermine teaching and teachers' work persist and need to be effectively addressed. Implementing educational changes requires not only legislative reforms, but also investments in school infrastructure, continuing teacher education, salary improvements, and better working conditions.

For Brazilian High School to more effectively fulfill its role in student development, it is necessary to expand spaces for dialogue and participation among teachers, students, and society in the formulation and implementation of educational policies. Reforms must consider the reality of schools, the needs of the students, and teachers' health and working conditions.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that the quality of education is directly linked to the appreciation of teachers. An educational policy committed to the right to learning must recognize that there is no quality education without decent working conditions, professional recognition, and a State that truly prioritizes public education. Building a socially referenced High School system implies reaffirming education as a right rather than a service, and teachers' work as a central pillar of a more just and egalitarian society.

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